

TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON MODERN METHODS

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Abstract: this article is about the methodology of teaching a foreign language, its science as the history of development, modern used in foreign language teaching methodology method types and their use are mentioned.

Keywords: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, qualification, didactics.

Introduction

Today's era educational development new direction innovative pedagogy caused. Innovator-English meaning “introducing (spreading) a novelty” may refer to means. Socio-psychological aspect of innovating American researcher E. Designed by Rodgers. He noted that the participants of the innovation process studied classification, their attitude to novelty, etc. Scientific in the directions, the concepts of innovation and innovation differ. “Novelty”- it means a tool, a new method, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is education is a process that develops according to certain stages. The development of World Science is gaining momentum and development day by day. It is this positive development has also taken its toll on our home.

The main of the results

Advanced to our world of science innovative technologies are being implemented. As a performance of this, our country Master by the current year as the “Year of youth support and Population Health” the naming also increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. Education the widespread implementation of advanced, modern innovative technologies in their fields is also wide opportunities for young people learning a foreign language, opened the door to milestones, there will be no mistake to say. Language learning is one of the most important areas of tolerance in the human society. The language, which is a means of communication, can be used in a natural environment, either in the family, among the public or practical possession is possible in an organized way. And knowledge of linguistic phenomena is theoretical taught in terms. Knowledge of languages at the height of international relations, multilingualism in particular is of immense

importance. Studying in our country students and students typically learn three languages. These languages have special names is maintained. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue thinking it is considered the first language that is served separately in its formation.

About the second language when spoken, it is preceded by a cognate of other nationalities, the language of the neighbours regarded as. №3 2022 182 A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western Europe in our republic (English, Spanish, German, Persian) languages and Oriental (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Hindi) languages were taught are coming. These languages are adapted from educational plans of educational institutions. All three the language teaching process is varied. Mother tongue and second language in a natural situation, a foreign language is studied in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language, mainly a teacher in the lesson leads. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language is specific differs sharply in aspects. This, in turn, is due to Foreign Language Teaching it assumes the application of its technology. Foreign language teacher achievements in methodology science clear the norm of language experience accumulated by a student-student through thorough mastering achieves knowledge and its further refinement. Effective teaching of foreign languages it requires knowledge of its methodology. A lot of learning and teaching foreign languages to the theoretical elaboration of issues of foreign language study methodology in terms of and depends on the creative application of the theory in practice. The main concepts of methodology are Method, method, principle. Didactics - what teach? training is content. Methodology-how do we teach? education means methods and techniques. The concept of method – methodology is Greek-Latin "metodos is derived from the word "metodus" meaning paths to a specific goal, method meaning. Meeting the narrow and broad meaning of the term in various literature can. The term "methodology" is narrowly defined by the concrete course process of Education refers to a related concept. Training planning and training materials guided lesson covering instructions related to preparation is interpreted as a process. The term “method” broadly refers to the teaching material implies selection, stratification and distribution. Federal Of Germany In the Republic since the 60s, “didactics” and “methodics” are in a narrow sense applied. Accordingly, what is the content of didactic education taught? And methodology, how are educational methods taught? Deals with issues. Foreign

learning languages is not just a means of mental education, but a culture other than educational to get acquainted with their wealth and values and to introduce them into their cultural life through is the process of formation of a person's personality. Foreign languages in Europe learning is considered a privilege in obtaining a high level of education for a long time and public it is considered to be the education of people who have the privilege in their schools.

Foreign language teaching method-practical teaching of a foreign language when said, ensuring the achievement of universal, educational and developmental goals a complex of teacher and student activities is understood. The term method refers to " education the sum of methods is used in the sense of “and” direction of Education". One in educational theory, a process is used in the sense of methods, while in the second sense it is used by we can find in works on the history of teaching methodology. For example, a foreign language translation method of teaching, mountain method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, is an intensive method, etc. №3 2022 183 Method without translation. Various manifestations of this method are historically known. Them it can be divided into two large groups: natural and mountain methods. Edge in natural method learning a language should be a similar to the conditions of acquiring a native language. Method's head the goal is to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language the idea that an opportunity will be created is formed in a practical goal. Natural method the most important of the principles included in the composition is the creation of a language environment. Advanced various approaches have appeared in the chapter on the practical application of methodological principles. Method this can be clearly noticed in the creative activity of their manifestations. In a new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education, mainly, the results of pragmatic Linguistics Research were relied on.

This area of linguistics interprets language as an area of human activity rather than a linguistic form system. Foreign language new conclusions in the field of Education, which began to accumulate since the beginning of the 70s the set led to heated discussions in the field of setting the educational goal. Foreign the goal of determining the main directions of language education is to “treat” students teaching to do, "Befaeigung zur Kommunikatik" (kommunikative Kompetenz new training plans were adopted. In the 1970s, the “communicative method” included one after a series of attempts, he found his proof in several stages. So asnoda the science of

methodology has evolved. No foreign language we deepen its methodology we cannot occupy without learning. In foreign language teaching methodology “communicative the method “didactics” is also considered significant. Communicative didactics embodies the following.

Conclusion

To conclude, foreign language learning is a multifaceted doctrine, in the process of which a person is complex experiences psychological changes. Including a foreign language with a native language a comparison process occurs. The different method of teaching in this process and technologies are used. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies teaching by comparing a foreign language with a native language gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language it assumes knowledge of his methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. The lesson there are different methods of methodological Science in the organization. In foreign language teaching methodology widely used methods: method of communicative didactics, intercultural communication organization method and exercise organization method are considered. Since the subject of methodology is related to the science of didactics, foreign language learning during the communicativity is based and communicative didactics method occurs.

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